

Heavier Alkali-metal Gallates as Platforms for Accessing Functionalized Abnormal NHC Carbene-Gallium Complexes

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Abstract. By sequentially treating the unsaturated carbene IPr [IPr = 1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene] with heavier alkali-metal alkyls NaR or KR ($R = \text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$) and GaR_3 , novel heteroleptic gallates **1** and **2** were prepared. Incorporating anionic NHC ligands, these bimetallic complexes react selectively with electrophiles to afford neutral abnormal NHC Ga complexes under mild conditions.

Introduction

N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs), particularly imidazol-2-ylidenes, have played a pivotal role in advancing key areas of modern chemistry including transition-metal catalysis,^[1] stabilization of low valent main-group compounds,^[2] and the development of frustrated Lewis pair systems,^[3] to name just a few. By modifying the substituents on the N atoms or at the backbone of the imidazole ring, the electronic and steric properties of NHCs can be finely tuned, making these commodity ligands extremely versatile.^[4,5] Typically imidazol-2-ylidenes bind to metal fragments through their C2 (normal) position although in some cases coordination can occur via a carbon from the imidazole backbone (C4 or abnormal coordination).^[4,5] NHCs can also exist as anionic moieties, as the result of their formal deprotonation, acting as a bridge between two metal centres employing simultaneously their C2 and C4 positions.^[6] Interestingly, Robinson has shown that electrophilic interception of anionic NHC complexes with MeOTf or $\text{HCl}\cdot\text{NEt}_3$ can be employed to prepare abnormal NHC complexes (*a*NHCs) of B and Zn.^[7] More recently our group has also used a similar approach for the synthesis of *a*NHC complexes of Ga and Fe, where the normal C2 position of the carbene is blocked by a methyl group.^[8,9] Carbanionic NHCs can be prepared by several methods including chemical reduction and metal-mediated C–H activation, however deprotonative metallation appears to be one of the most versatile approaches.^[10]

The vast majority of the studies on NHC metallation has focussed on using organolithium reagents as a base,^[6,8] al-

though mixed-metal systems such as zincates and magnesiates have shown great promise for the zincation or magnesiation of IPr [IPr = 1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene].^[11,12] Extending the scope of these investigations herein we explore the metallating ability of heavier alkali-metal alkyls to prepare gallate complexes containing anionic NHC fragments and their applications to access novel *a*NHCs Ga complexes with a variety of substituents.

Results and Discussion

We started our studies by employing heavier alkali-metal alkyls NaR and KR ($R = \text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$) for direct metallation of IPr as this methodology seems to be underdeveloped. Treating a hexane suspension of IPr with MR ($M = \text{Na}, \text{K}$), led to the instant formation of yellow solids, which were completely insoluble even when using large amounts of the more polar solvent THF. Interestingly, addition of GaR_3 solubilized these products allowing the isolation of heteroleptic alkali-metal gallates $(\text{THF})_3\text{Na}[\text{C}\{\text{N}(2,6\text{-}i\text{Pr}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3)_2\text{CHCGa}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_3\}]$ (**1**) and $(\text{THF})_3\text{K}[\text{C}\{\text{N}(2,6\text{-}i\text{Pr}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3)_2\text{CHCGa}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_3\}]$ (**2**) in 71 and 76% isolated yields respectively (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Stepwise indirect gallation of IPr affording alkali-metal gallates **1** and **2**.

Formation of gallates **1** and **2** can be rationalized in terms of a stepwise indirect gallation process. IPr is first deprotonated at the C4 position by the highly polar MR reagent (**I** in

Scheme 1), which can undergo fast transmetalation with the more electronegative Ga fragment, with the alkali-metal being trapped by the vacant C2 site of the carbene (Scheme 1). Although the solids obtained by treating IPr with *MR* cannot be characterized, due to their lack of solubility, the isolation of **1** and **2** provides compelling proof that these heavier alkaline metal alkyls can in fact metallate this NHC. Interestingly, when the single metal alkyl reagents are combined to form tetraorganogallates $MGaR_4$,^[13] the metallation process is inhibited yielding instead the coordination adducts $[IPr_2K][GaR_4]$ (see Supporting Information for details), which highlights the potential of using bimetallic systems in a sequential manner.^[14] While the relevant M^+IPr^- salts (**1**) are obtained via direct metallation, it should be noted that *Goicoechea* et al. have structurally characterized $K^+IPr^- \cdot 2THF$ as the result of the reaction of the lithiated IPr with potassium *tert*-butoxide.^[15]

Both sodium (**1**) and potassium gallate (**2**) exhibit discrete contacted ion-pair (CIP) structures, where anionic NHC ligand coordinates to the alkali metal through its normal C2 position, while Ga occupies the position previously filled by a hydrogen atom, bonding to the C4 position (Figure 1). The Ga–C4 distances (i.e. C24 for **1** and C2 for **2** in Figure 1) of 2.050(2) Å for **1** and 2.050(3) Å for **2** are close in value with the Ga–C_{alkyl} bonds (average 2.027 Å and 2.028 Å for **1** and **2**, respectively) and they are also in excellent agreement with the bond lengths found in the previously reported lithium congener.^[8] The narrow variation observed for the Ga–C bond lengths together with very similar bond angles (mean angle 108.15° for **1** and 109.46° for **2**) reveal an almost ideal tetrahedral arrangement of the central gallium atom in both compounds. With the virtually identical environment around Ga atom, complexes **1** and **2** display their differences at the other end of the bridging ligand.

Unsurprisingly, the $M-C_{NHC}$ bond length found in **1** [2.530(3) Å] is significantly shorter than that of **2** [2.902(3) Å], which is in agreement with the increase in size of the alkali metal. Both values compare well with those reported for other anionic complexes containing these alkali metals.^[9,11,13,16,17] Both sodium and potassium complete their coordination spheres by coordination of three molecules of THF, with more electropositive potassium gaining further stabilization through electrostatic interaction with the *ipso* carbon of the pendant Dipp group on N2 (Figure 1). This secondary contact [$K1 \cdots C16 = 3.301(3)$ Å] is within the range of previously reported potassium π interactions^[18] and translates into a significantly more acute N2–C1–K1 angle [107.77(18)°] than N1–C1–K1 [150.71(19)°].

From the NMR spectroscopic data of **1** and **2** in $[D_8]THF$ solutions, the metallation of IPr is evident by the large downfield shift of the C4 resonance in the ¹³C NMR spectra (from 122.3 in free IPr to 155.2 and 153.6 ppm respectively) as well as the presence of a diagnostic singlet integrating 1H in the ¹H NMR spectra for the imidazole CH (at $\delta = 6.64$ and 6.59 ppm, respectively, versus 7.19 in free IPr). The loss of symmetry in the imidazole ring is reflected in the ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra with the appearance of two distinct sets of Dipp signals. In addition, the carbenic C atom attached to the alkali metal can

Figure 1. Molecular structure of **1** (top) and **2** (bottom) with 50 % probability displacement ellipsoids. All hydrogen atoms except the one left on imidazole ring and disorder components in THF ligands are omitted for clarity. Dashed lines represent secondary interactions.

be observed at $\delta = 202.8$ and 210.7 ppm for **1** and **2**, respectively, at similar values to those reported for other related complexes containing Na^[11] and K.^[15] The well-established notion that the size and the substitution pattern of the heterocyclic ring frame can have a large effect on the properties of carbene,^[18,19] prompted us to investigate the potential of **1** and **2** as molecular synthons.

To this end, **1** was reacted with an equimolar amount of allyl bromide and **2** with Me_3SiCl in THF at room temperature. In both cases the reaction proceeded with the formation of white precipitate (presumably alkali metal salts NaBr and KCl, respectively) affording $[C_3H_5C\{[N(2,6-iPr_2C_6H_3)]_2CHCGa(CH_2SiMe_3)_3\}]$ (**3**) and $[Me_3SiC\{[N(2,6-iPr_2C_6H_3)]_2CHCGa(CH_2SiMe_3)_3\}]$ (**4**) in 42 and 61 % yields, respectively (Scheme 2). Compounds **3** and **4** are neutral abnormal NHC Ga complexes obtained as a result of the selective allylation (for **3**) and silylation (for **4**) of the C2 position of the anionic NHC ligand present in **1** and **2**, leaving the C4–Ga left intact.

The isolation of **4** contrasts with the reactivity reported by *Arnold* et al. for a related mixed K/Y complex,^[16] where the silylation occurs at the C4 position of the anionic carbene, instead of C2. Similar regioselectivity has been witnessed by *Robinson* and co-workers for polymeric Li^+IPr^- , which in this case affords the C4– SiMe_3 substituted free carbene.^[6] Interestingly, by adding borane to this lithium complex, it is possible to direct the selectivity of the quench with SiMe_3Cl towards C2.^[7b]

Scheme 2. Electrophilic interception of anionic NHC complexes (a) **1** with allyl bromide and (b) **2** with Me_3SiCl .

The molecular structures of **3** and **4** were established by X-ray crystallography (Figure 2). The Ga–C4 distances (i.e. C3 and C45 for **3** and **4**, respectively) showed very little variation [2.0802(18) and 2.0887(16) Å] to that found in $[\text{aIPr}\cdot\text{GaR}_3]$ ^[8] [2.0759(16) Å], where the C2 position of the carbene is occupied by a hydrogen atom, suggesting that the substituents on the C2 of the imidazole ring have little influence in the strength of the Ga–C4 bond. Another interesting trend is that despite the neutral constitution of these novel abnormal NHCs, the Ga–C bond lengths are only slightly elongated to those discussed for the anionic precursors **1** and **2**. Structural analysis of **3** revealed it to be a cocrystal, which contains $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$ and $\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_3$ as substituents at the C2 of the carbene in approximately 2:3 ratio, arising from the partial allylic rearrangement. Mirroring this composition in the solution, NMR spectroscopic analysis of **3** proved to be extremely complex in the allylic section (from 3 to 6 ppm); although it should be noted that no interconversion between these two isomers is observed over prolonged periods of time. Despite its complexity, the ^1H NMR spectrum displays four septets for the CH of isopropyl groups, whereas an informative resonance at $\delta = 163.4$ ppm is observed for the carbenic carbon. A similar chemical shift was observed for **4** ($\delta = 167.6$ ppm) along with another signal at $\delta = 148.8$ ppm, which can be assigned to the C of the imidazole ring that is now bonded to a SiMe_3 group.

Collectively these findings show the ability of heavier alkali metal alkyls to effectively metallate unsaturated NHC IPr when operating in tandem with a gallium alkyl, affording sodium and potassium gallate complexes **1** and **2**, respectively.

Figure 2. Molecular structure of **3** (top) and **4** (bottom) with 50 % probability displacement ellipsoids. All hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. For compound **3** only the $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$ fragment is shown. The unit cell of **4** contains three crystallographically independent molecules with identical connectivity. One of these molecules is shown here.

Electrophilic interception of these bimetallic compounds selectively yielded neutral abnormal Ga NHC complexes disclosing the preference of anionic ligand present in **1** and **2** to react with electrophiles by its C2 position while preserving the Ga–C4 bond.

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